

Washington and Lee University
Field Reports
Florence As It Was

Title: LiDAR Scans and the Point Cloud Model of the Palazzo della Signoria,
Florence:
43.76931, 11.25605

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Field Team:

George R. Bent
Scott McAvoy
Lorenzo Vigotti

Data Collection:

17-21 April 2025
23-30 June 2025

Data Processing Team:

George R. Bent
Mickie Brown
David Pfaff
Scott McAvoy

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David Pfaff
Director
IQ Center
Washington and Lee University
Lexington, Virginia (USA)

George Bent, Ph.D
Sidney Gause Childress Professor of the Arts
Department of Art and Art History
Washington and Lee University
Lexington, Virginia (USA)

The Palazzo Vecchio stands at the east edge of the Piazza della Signoria, a space created by the razed homes of Ghibelline families ousted from power after 1266. The oldest portion of the palace was built in short order, between 1298 and 1302, and housed the six (then, later, eight) guildsmen selected to govern the city for two-month terms. The rusticated exterior intentionally suggests a fortress mentality, while the battlements, crenellations, and bell tower underscore the building's dual roles as keeper of the peace and protector of the Republic. The portal on the building's west façade leads directly into the central courtyard designed by Michelozzo in 1453. This in turn leads, first, to the opposing staircases that lead to the upper stories (built in the fourteenth century, altered in the fifteenth, sixteenth, and nineteenth centuries) and then on to the Cortile della Dogana (Courtyard of the Customs Officials) that today serves as a buffer between the historic building and the sixteenth-century addition that today serves as the bureaucratic offices of the Florentine government.

The labyrinthine interior today houses art objects, early modern furnishings, and curiosities befitting an Italian museum. Of primary importance are the Sala dei 500 (built at the very end of the 15th century) on the Piano Nobile, the fourteenth-century Sala dei Giglio on the floor above, and the Cappella d'Eleonora, decorated by Bronzino in the 1540s.

Project Overview:

With permission from the Communal Government of Florence and Giorgio Casali, City Architect, and with the generous assistance of Fabio Sforzi, data was collected at the Palazzo Vecchio. The goals of this project were:

1. Scan the entirety of the church exterior, cloisters, nave, and loggia of the church.
2. Transmit data to the IQ Center at W&L.
3. Edit and model SS. Annunziata for insertion into the Digital Humanities Project *Florence As It Was*

Written authorization from the Comune of Florence (March 2022) granted permission to work inside the churches of SS. Annunziata and S. Spirito.

Data Acquisition:

Equipment

Leica BLK360 Laser Scanner: The battery operated BLK360 rotates twice on a tripod. The first three-minute rotation uses a laser beam to capture surfaces in its path with a range of 40m. The second two-minute rotation takes photographs from three cameras, the color and images from which are mapped onto the points generated by the laser. All scans were taken at the Medium Density setting.

Leica RTC360 Laser Scanner: The battery operated RTC360 rotates twice on a tripod. The first sixty-second rotation uses a laser beam to capture surfaces in its path with a maximum range of 80m. The second sixty-second rotation takes photographs from three cameras, the color and images from which are mapped onto the points generated by the laser. All scans were taken at the Medium Density setting.

iPad and Software: The scanner is controlled by an iPad through Cyclone Register 360 (CR360) software. Scans are aligned on site to form models that reveal areas covered (and unscanned) in real time.

Data Quality and Availability

The data provided by this project is not certified by a licensed surveyor. If an application requires a high level of accuracy (for example, a hydrological analysis) please contact the author of this report.

Activities

17-18, 20-21 April 2025

George Bent took 473 scans with the Leica RTC360 unit (Medium density) from 17-21 April. Moving from the foundations to the Museum level of the Palace, the following sections of the building were scanned accordingly:

17 April – Stairs from the piano terreno to the piano nobile (49 scans); foundations beneath the building (69 scans)

18 April – Piazza (38), Cortile Michelozzo (11), Cortile della Dogana (32), Foundations (Roman ruins) (35 + 48)

20 April – Architect's offices (59), terrace (7), Sala dei 200 (30), exterior (via della Ninna) (36)

21 April – Stairs from piano nobile to the supper floors (21), Mezzanine (38)

23-30 June 2025

George Bent, Scott McAvoy, and Lorenzo Vigotti worked together to scan the remainder of the Palazzo Vecchio and its bell tower, with Bent using the Leica RTC360 and McAvoy and Vigotti using the BLK360 to take 472 scans. Vigotti assisted in scanning the top of the campanile on 27 June.

23 June – Terrace (54 scans)

24 June – Sala dei 500 (25 scans), Museum rooms (77)

25 June – Tower (87),

26 June – Merli (47), south staircase (secret passage) (46)

27 June – southwest corner (21), secondo piano – Architect’s offices (28), Opificio (22)

29 June – east wing (8), Studiolo (8) rafters (55), tunnel beneath courtyard (7)

With temperatures approaching dangerous levels, considerable care was taken to hydrate and rest. At two junctures – June 24 and June 27 – conditions caused physical reactions in Bent, who completed projects in great discomfort.

Editing, Summer 2025

George Bent, Mickie Brown, David Pfaff, and Scott McAvoy edited 1045 individual scans in Cyclone Register 360 (CR360) to address image quality, alignment, and deletion of extraneous points. This process resulted in the creation of holes in the model, primarily in the Mezzanine rooms that are currently used by the building’s architects.

Challenges and Solutions

Major challenges posed significant obstacles to be overcome.

1. The Palazzo Vecchio serves as both a museum and as the headquarters of the city government. Significant areas in the foundations, piano nobile, and Mezzanine levels are filled with modern furnishings that could not be moved during the scanning process.
2. The Sala dei 200 functions as a conference center and is filled with tables and electronic equipment.
3. The Sala dei 500 has a reflective tile floor that discolors scans.
4. The violet wall coverings on the piano nobile, particularly the Sala degli Gigli, and the large windows caused significant discolorations.
5. The rafters above the Sala dei 500 can only be scanned from central positions due to the severe slant of the roofline.
6. The top floor holds the restoration lab of the Opificio. Out of respect for the sensitive nature of their work, all objects inside the vast room had to be deleted.
7. The building's height prevented appropriate data capturing from ground level. Drone flights in Florence are currently prohibited.
8. The top of the campanile was sealed shut and could not be opened by Fabio Sforzi or George Bent.

The solutions to these challenges – in the field and during the editing phase in the IQ Lab at W&L – were partially successful.

1. Modern furnishings were edited out of all rooms currently used by journalists, museum and government staff, and restorers. This has left holes in the point cloud.
2. Photographs have been altered in the HDR settings to address discolorations.
3. Small openings in the walls of the top floor were wide enough to permit the slender BLK360 unit (used by Scott McAvoy) to slide through. Attached to a 10m pole, the BLK was pushed out of the walls, held steady by Lorenzo Vigotti, and then employed to scan the exterior walls from close range.
4. Thanks to the collaborative spirit of Remote Sensing professionals, a previous point cloud of the top of the campanile was shared by Giorgio Verdiani (UniFi) and stitched onto our model.

The completed model – the largest produced by *Florence As It Was* to date – is formed by 2,122,278,110 points and consumes **437 gb of data** (<https://wlu.app.box.com/folder/208330603673>).

The resulting model may be inspected at: <https://3d.wlu.edu/v21/pages/Vecchio/Vecchio.html>